

Health Information Communication used in the Prevention of Malaria in Jere Local Government Area of Borno State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: This study evaluates the role of health information communication in preventing malaria in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria, focusing on its effectiveness in raising awareness and promoting health.

Method: A survey design was employed, with two objectives, research questions, and hypotheses formulated. Using simple random sampling, 234 heads of households in Gwange ward were selected from a population of 621, based on the Krejcie and Morgan table. Data were collected via a self-developed questionnaire divided into three sections (A, B, and C). Frequency counts and percentages addressed the research questions, while Chi-square inferential statistics tested the hypotheses.

Findings/Results: The study found that health information communication effectively informs households about malaria, its characteristics, and transmission modes, contributing to infection prevention.

Implications: Effective communication strategies enhance public awareness and understanding of malaria, supporting health promotion and disease prevention efforts.

Conclusion: Health information communication serves as an effective policy tool, enabling households to access critical information about malaria, thereby reducing infection rates and improving community health.

Recommendations: The government should implement regular awareness campaigns on malaria transmission and conduct routine environmental fumigation to sustain prevention efforts.

Keywords: Health Information Communication, Prevention, Malaria

Introduction

Communication is an integral aspect of interventions that seek to address individual, community and social factors and can have a significant impact on many levels of health intervention implementation. It is a transactional process, which in health context plays an important part in health promotion. Communication is extremely important in the fight against malaria not only because it offers considerable instrumental value, but also because it facilitates access to

interventions that aid the prevention, treatment and care for the ailment. It will also reduce vulnerability to the disease, improve advocacy, and subsequently enhance mobilization and networking (Okpoko & Aniwada, 2017).

According to Heggenhougen, Hackethal & Vivek (2003), in the health dimension, malaria leaves untold social and economic consequences on people and nations alike. It causes great misery to sufferers, and adversely affects the social and psychological well-being of individuals, families and the nation at large both behavioral and non-behavioral factors account for the prevalence of malaria in Borno State. Some cultural practices, which promote mosquito breeding and mosquitoes access to the people, and the failure of at-risk populations to use technologies required for effective treatment, control and prevention of malaria promptly and appropriately etc. have been implicated for the continued prevalence of malaria in these parts (Ambe, et al., 2020). Added to the list is “lack of political will commitment, poor perception of the magnitude of the malaria burden and poor treatment seeking behaviors of individuals and communities” (Nevill, 1996). The problem became more aggravated following the evolution of the parasites and vectors that are resistant to medicines and insecticides. The geographical or ecological conditions of our region have been advanced as being very conducive for mosquitoes and the subsequent presence of plasmodia. It is therefore pertinent to understand the dynamics and implications of these factors to enable us design appropriate intervention programs for tackling malaria in our societies.

It is argued that home management of malaria along with public information and Pre-Packaged Drugs (PPDs) can help to reduce malaria morbidity and mortality in children. The PPDs ensure that full treatment course is taken by patients and at the right time. Furthermore, in collaboration with other states, Borno State signed the Declaration and Plan of Action in 2000 to reduce the burden of the disease by half in the year 2010. Among the actions identified are: prompt diagnosis and treatment with effective medicines, distribution of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) to populations at risk (especially children under age five and pregnant women), indoor residual spraying (IRS) to curtail transmission, and prevention of malaria in pregnancy through intermittent preventive treatment (IPT) (WHO, 2016). It must be

stressed that the main contents of the prevention program revolve around advocacy, behavior change communication and social mobilization. In essence, the strategic frameworks for malaria communication have been developed to ensure adequate awareness and utilization of interventions in Nigeria (Ambe, Balogun, Waziri, Nglass, & Saddiq, 2020).

According to Maslove, Mnyusiwalla, Mills, McGowan, Attaran and Wilson (2009), a systematic review of articles on barriers to the effective treatment and prevention of malaria in Africa over three decades revealed that lack of understanding of the cause and transmission of malaria constitutes the most critical barrier to malaria prevention, the use of ineffective prevention measures, and the belief that malaria cannot be prevented. They also noted that the belief that a child with convulsion could die if given an injection or taken to hospital, is a major barrier to the treatment of childhood malaria. Indeed, and as reported by Maslove, (2009), any successful effort at prevention and treatment of malaria in every society must take cognizance of the overall social and cultural contexts, namely their values, belief systems and norms.

Isah, Ambe, Bobga, Ketum, Ivan and Abungwi (2020) result show that the increased ITBN usage, increased parents/guardians' educational level and good knowledge of ITBN is required to lower the risk of under-five children being infected with malaria. These, therefore, indicates the possession of ITBN doesn't mean their usage. Dingley, Daugherty, Derieg and Persing (2008) that improving patient safety through provider communication strategy enhancements. Advances in patient safety: new directions and alternative approaches which come up with the result reveals that ineffective or insufficient communication among team members is a significant contributing factor to adverse events. In the acute care setting, communication failures lead to increases in patient harm, length of stay, and resource use, as well as more intense caregiver dissatisfaction and more rapid turnover.

Patel & Patel (2017) stated that communication is the best tool to successfully achievement of objective of any intervention focused on solving public health issues. In public health there exist many communication strategies but the most

effective is the storytelling communication strategy. Story telling is a way in which message is conveyed to people in the form of narrating stories. The mode of storytelling can be electronic, verbal or printed form. In past decade mode of communication has evolved. Nyiam and Ngwu (2020) stated that mass media especially the broadcast media, played remarkable roles in the sensitisation and mobilisation of the people against malaria. It was concluded that communication is an indispensable aspect of the malaria intervention programmes which has equally improved the utilization of insecticide treated nets, but the strategies in use need improvement and extended to rural parts of the state.

Use of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) is one of the key components of malaria prevention and control as recommended by the World Health Organization (2003). The nets lessen human contact with mosquitoes, subsequently prompting a noteworthy decrease in the incidence of malaria, related morbidity, and mortality; just as in the unfriendly impacts during pregnancy in regions of extreme malaria transmission. This is where communication intervention becomes intrinsically very relevant to enable us educating them on the causative factors of malaria, as well as the treatment regimens.

Statement of the Problem

Communication is extremely important in the fight against Malaria not only because it offers considerable instrumental value, but also because it facilitates access to interventions that aid the prevention, treatment and care for the ailment. It will also reduce vulnerability to the disease, improve advocacy, and subsequently enhance mobilization and networking. Mass media of communication has been a force that exerts great influence on the society.

Malaria is endemic in Nigeria and in Maiduguri, which is one of the cause and consequence of underdevelopment and remains one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality in the State. It is on this note that this study sets to assess the health information communication in the prevention of malaria in Jere Local Government, Maiduguri Borno State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study are to:

- i. Determine the health information communication in fighting malaria in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria.
- ii. Determine relevance of health information communication in the prevention of malaria in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following questions are explored in this study

1. What are the of health information communication in fighting malaria in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria?
2. What is the relevance of health information communication in the prevention of malaria in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

Ho1: The sources of health information communication in the fighting of malaria in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria is not significant.

Ho2: The relevance of health information communication in the fighting of malaria in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria is not significant.

Methodology

The research design adopted in this study was survey design. Survey design are those studies which aim at collecting data on, and describing the data in a systematic manner using the characteristics, features and facts about a given population. Cohens, Manion and Morrison (2009) said that, survey is used to scan wider field of issues, population and program in order to measure and generalize the findings of a study and hence it is considered economically and efficient.

The population of this study comprised of six hundred and twenty one (621) head of household in Gwange ward, Jere Local Government Area of Maiduguri Borno state, Nigeria. Simple random sampling technique was used to select two hundred and thirty (234) respondents using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table sample for sample specification.

The instrument was self-developed questionnaire. It is divided into three sections A, B, and C with fourteen (14) questions. The respondents were expected to respond to the items on a modified 4-point Likert scale of Strongly agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), strongly disagree (1).

The researchers administered the questionnaire within the period of six days, after which the completed questionnaires were retrieved for data analysis. The respondents were assured of their anonymity for the research purpose.

The copies of the retrieved questionnaires that have been treated properly was sorted out and analyzed. Frequency count and percentages was used to test the research questions while the test of hypotheses was carried out using inferential statistics of Chi-square. The basis for the acceptance or rejection of hypothesis was 0.05 alpha level of significant.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Information of the Respondents (n=230)

S/No.	Item	Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Age	20-30	69	30.00
		31-40	56	24.35
		41-50	75	32.61
		51 & above	30	13.04
		Total	230	100
2.	Gender	Male	162	70.44
		Female	68	29.56
		Total	230	100
3.	Marital Status	Single	112	48.69
		Married	79	34.35
		Separated	23	10.00

	Widow	16	6.96
	Total	230	100
4. Educational Background	F.S.L.C	98	42.60
	O Level	56	24.35
	B.Sc/B.A	41	17.83
	PhD	4	1.74
	Others	31	13.48
	Total	230	100

Table 1 shows that 69 (30.00%) of the respondents were between the age of 20-30 years, 56 (24.35%) were between the ages of 31-40 years, 75 (32.61%) of the respondents were between the age of 41-50 years and 30 (13.04%) were between the age of 51 and above. The table indicates that 162 (70.44%) of the respondents were male, while 68 (29.56%) were female. Furthermore, the table shows that 112 (48.69%) of the respondent were single, 79 (34.35%) of the respondents were married, 23 (10.00%) of the participant were separated, while 16 (6.96%) of the respondents were widow. The table also indicates that 98 (42.60%) of the respondents had completed just their primary education, 56 (24.35%) of the respondents had O level certificate, 41 (17.83%) of the respondents are degree holders, while 4 (1.74%) and 31 (13.48%) had PhD and others respectively.

Research Question One: What is the Health Information Communication used in prevention of Malaria in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Health Information Communication used for the Prevention of Malaria.
n= 230

S/No.	Item	Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
5.	Community mobilization on use of malaria drugs is a strategy in fighting malaria.	SA	85	36.96
		A	65	28.26
		D	46	20.00
		SD	34	14.78
		Total	230	100
6.	Giving information on treated bed net is a strategy in fighting malaria.	SA	100	43.48
		A	70	30.43
		D	41	17.83
		SD	19	8.26
		Total	230	100
7.	Giving information on vector control is a strategy in fighting malaria.	SA	102	44.35
		A	80	34.78
		D	30	13.04
		SD	18	7.83
		Total	230	100
8.	Use of insecticide is a strategy in fighting malaria.	SA	118	51.30
		A	80	34.78
		D	29	12.61
		SD	3	1.31
		Total	230	100
9.	Getting information through radio and television on insecticide help to prevent malaria	SA	41	17.83
		A	30	13.04
		D	98	42.61
		SD	61	26.52
		Total	230	100

Table 2 which determine the sources of health information for the prevention of malaria shows that 150 (65.22%) of the respondents agreed that community

mobilization on use of malaria drugs is a strategy in fighting malaria, while 80 (34.78%) disagreed with the statement. Giving information on treated bed net is a strategy in fighting malaria shows that 170 (73.91%) of the respondents agreed with the statement, while 60 (26.09%) disagreed. Giving information on vector control is a strategy in fighting malaria shows that 182 (79.13%) of the respondents agreed to the statement, while 48 (20.87%) disagreed with the statement. 198 (86.18%) agreed that the use of insecticide is a strategy in fighting malaria, while 32 (13.92%) disagreed with the statement. The table also indicates that 71 (31.87%) of the respondents agreed that getting information through radio and television on insecticide helps to prevent malaria, while 159 (69.13%) disagreed to the statement.

Research Question Two: What is the relevance of Health Information Communication in the Prevention of Malaria in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria?

Table 3: Relevance of Health Information Communication in the Prevention of Malaria.

S/No.	Item	Response	Freq	(%)
10.	Keeping our environment clean is one of the relevance of ICS in prevention of malaria	SA	100	43.48
		A	76	33.04
		D	33	14.35
		SD	21	9.13
		Total	230	100
11.	Creating awareness is one of the relevance of ICS in prevention of malaria	SA	104	45.22
		A	50	21.74
		D	50	21.74
		SD	26	11.30
		Total	230	100
12.	Does fumigating our environment with insecticide is one of the	SA	126	54.78
		A	60	26.09
		D	34	14.78

relevance of ICS in prevention of malaria	SD	10	4.35
	Total	230	100
13. Watching programs on malaria prevention is one of the relevance of ICS in prevention of malaria	SA	75	32.61
	A	35	15.22
	D	96	41.74
	SD	24	10.73
	Total	230	100
14. Getting information through internet on environmental sanitation is one of the relevance of ICS in prevention of malaria	SA	41	17.83
	A	15	6.52
	D	107	46.52
	SD	67	29.13
	Total	230	100

Table 3 shows that 176 (76.52%) of the respondents agreed that keeping the environment clean is one of the relevance of information communication in prevention of malaria, while 54 (23.48%) disagreed with the statement. Creating awareness is one of the relevance of information communication in prevention of malaria shows that 154 (66.96%) of the respondents agreed to the statement, while 76 (33.04%) disagreed with the statement. The table indicates that 186 (80.87%) of the respondents agreed that fumigating our environment with insecticide is one of the relevance of information communication in prevention of malaria, while 44 (19.13%) disagreed with the statement. The table shows that 110 (47.83%) of the respondents agreed that watching programs on malaria prevention is one of the relevance of information communication in prevention of malaria, while 120 (52.17%) of the respondents disagreed with the statement. The table also indicates that 56 (24.35%) of the respondents agreed that information through internet on environmental sanitation is one of the relevance of information communication in prevention of malaria, while 174 (75.65%) of the respondents disagreed to the statement. The majority of the respondents agreed that the relevance of Health Information Communication in the Prevention of Malaria.

Ho₁ *Sources of health information communication in the fighting of malaria in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria is not significant.*

Table 4: Chi-square Summary on sources of Health Information Communication in the Fighting of Malaria

Responses	Observed	Expected	χ^2 Cal	Df	$\chi^2_{critical}$	P value
Strongly Agreed	118	57.5				
Agreed	80	57.5	42.81	3	7.815	0.005
Disagreed	29	57.5				
Strongly Disagreed	3	57.5				

The table above indicates that the sources of health information communication in the fighting of malaria is significant. The results revealed that the calculated χ^2 42.81 is greater than χ^2 Critical value of 7.815 of df 3 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected that sources of health information communication in the fighting of malaria in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria is significant.

Ho₂ *The relevance of health information communication in the fighting of malaria in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria is not significant.*

Table 5: Chi-square Summary on Relevance of Health Information Communication in the Fighting of Malaria

Responses	Observed	Expected	χ^2 Cal	Df	$\chi^2_{critical}$	P value
Strongly Agreed	112	57.5				
Agreed	74	57.5	28.04	3	7.815	0.001
Disagreed	31	57.5				
Strongly Disagreed	3	57.5				

The table above indicates that the relevance of health information communication in the fighting of malaria is significant. The results revealed that the calculated χ^2 28.04 is greater than χ^2 Critical value of 7.815 of df 3 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected that relevance of health information

communication in the fighting of malaria in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria is significant.

Discussion

The study was designed to assess health information communication in the prevention of malaria in Jere Local Government Area, Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria. The findings of the study revealed that sources of health information communication in the fighting of malaria in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria is significant: This study is in line with the findings of Dingley, Daugherty, Derieg & Persing (2008) that improving patient safety through provider communication strategy enhancements. Advances in patient safety: new directions and alternative approaches which come up with the result reveals that ineffective or insufficient communication among team members is a significant contributing factor to adverse events. In the acute care setting, communication failures lead to increases in patient harm, length of stay, and resource use, as well as more intense caregiver dissatisfaction and more rapid turnover.

The finding also revealed that the relevance of health information communication strategy in the fighting of malaria in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria is significant. This is in line with the study of Patel & Patel (2017), who stated that communication is the best tool to successfully achieve an objective of any intervention focused on solving public health issues. In public health there exist many communication strategies but the most effective is the storytelling communication strategy. Story telling is a way in which message is conveyed to people in the form of narrating stories. The mode of storytelling can be electronic, verbal or printed form. In past decade mode of communication has evolved and also opposes the study of Nyiam and Ngwu (2020), who stated that mass media especially the broadcast media, played remarkable roles in the sensitization and mobilization of the people against malaria. It was concluded that communication is an indispensable aspect of the malaria intervention programmes which has equally improve the utilization of insecticide treated nets, but the strategies in use need improvement and extended to rural parts of the state.

Conclusion

It can be concluded that health information communication is an effective policies and guideline that every household can get access to the awareness of malaria it is characteristics and mode of transmission in order to prevent the occurrence of the infections and to promote their health status. Based on the study the answer reveal that relevance of health information communication in the fighting of malaria in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria is significant.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of the study, the following recommendations are as follows;

1. Regular awareness on the mode of transmission of malaria should be implemented by the government.
2. Routine fumigation of the environment with insecticides should be continuous encouraged to stop the multiplication of malaria vectors.
3. More mass media such as radio links, audiovisual, billboard and other print media should be adequately provided to make the sources of information accessible.
4. Non-governmental agencies also should be included in gathering the sources of information like pamphlet, article and jersey on the important of using mosquito net.

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